

TABLE III (contd.)

Temp.	$\eta \times 10^4$.	γ obs.	γ calc.	% Diff.	
	(b Ethyl acetate :	$P=216.0$.	$R=50.21$.	$(P/R)^4=342$	
0°	58.25	25.50	26.10	-2.4	
10	51.20	24.36	24.47	-0.6	
20	45.46	23.24	23.06	0.7	
30	40.72	21.81	21.82	-0.0	
40	36.69	20.78	20.72	-0.3	
50	33.34	19.60	19.75	-0.8	
60	30.45	18.61	18.87	-1.5	
70	27.80	17.70	18.05	-2.1	

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OXIDATION OF ARTOSTENONE WITH HYDROGEN PEROXIDE IN PRESENCE OF OSMIC ACID IN EXCESS

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A monoketo-monocarboxylic acid of artostenone has been prepared both from artostenone and dihydroxyartostanone. Its oxime, anilide and semicarbazone have been described.

It has previously been reported from this laboratory (Nath, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1937, 249, 71) that artostenone (I), the steroid ketone occurring in *Artocarpus integrifolia*, when oxidised with potassium permanganate in both neutral and acid medium, gives rise to the diketo-artostanic acid ($C_{30}H_{46}O_4$) (Nath, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1937, 247, 9). This also confirmed the hypothesis laid down by Windaus (*Ber.*, 1906, 39, 2008) towards the possible chemical changes in such process. Nath and Chakravorty (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 22, 19) have shown recently that artostenone forms an addition compound with hydrogen peroxide in presence of osmic acid, thus forming a dihydroxy compound (II).

It was observed that some amorphous powder was also obtained during this process, the yield of which varied with the proportion of osmic acid used. When osmic acid was added in trace, the yield of this amorphous powder was very low and the dihydroxy compound was obtained in abundance; while addition of the catalyst in excess gave rise to a greater yield of this amorphous powder. Hence, it was thought that the excess of osmic acid might have some effect in bringing about further chemical changes in the dihydroxy compound formed and giving rise to a new compound (III).

In order to verify this, the reactions were conducted with an excess of osmic acid on artostenone and also on the dihydroxy compound when osmic acid was added in trace. In both the reactions, the same amorphous powder was obtained which could ultimately be crystallised.

EXPERIMENTAL

Artostenone (1 g.) was dissolved in ether (100 c.c.) and treated with osmic acid (0.1 g.) in 10 c.c. of ether. Perhydrol (30 c.c.) was then added to the mixture, which was allowed to remain for 20 hours at ordinary temperature. The resulting solution was then allowed to evaporate completely and dried without application of heat, until the odour of osmic acid was removed. It was once again dissolved in ether and the solution was decolourised with one or two drops of perhydrol and evaporated. The colourless and semicrystalline residue after several crystallisations from 80% alcohol and then from methyl alcohol gave crystals melting at 88° . [Found: C, 77.93; H, 11.05; M.W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 442.6. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 78.02; H, 11.21 per cent. M.W., 446].

Preparation of derivatives.

(a) *Oxime*.—The substance (0.1 g.) was dissolved in 1 c.c. of alcohol and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.5 g.) and an excess of sodium acetate added. The mixture was then refluxed for 15 minutes, cooled, diluted with water and shaken with ether in a separating funnel. The solution on removal of ether left a solid residue, which was crystallised from absolute alcohol as needles, m.p. 165° . (Found: N, 3.2. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_3\text{N}$ requires N, 3.03 per cent).

(b) The *anilide* was prepared by refluxing for about 1 hour the substance (0.2 g.) with 2 c.c. of aniline and the mixture was then poured into ice but no precipitate was obtained. The whole thing was then heated on a water-bath, and most of the free aniline evaporated off. A sticky mass, thus obtained, was dissolved in methyl alcohol, the solution was warmed with norit, filtered and a few drops of water were added. On keeping for a few days, some stout transparent crystals separated out, which melt at 112° . (Found: N, 2.59. $\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{57}\text{O}_3\text{N}$ requires N, 2.59 per cent).

(c) *Semicarbazone*.—The substance (0.1 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (1 c.c.), and an aqueous alcoholic solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride (0.1 g.) and an excess of sodium acetate were added. The solution was refluxed for 6 hours on a water-bath, cooled and poured into water. A precipitate was obtained, which was filtered, washed repeatedly with water and finally crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 115-16°. (Found : N, 8.30. $C_{30}H_{53}O_3N_3$ requires N, 8.35 per cent).

DISCUSSION

It has previously been mentioned that artostenone on treatment with hydrogen peroxide in presence of osmic acid gives rise to dihydroxyartostanone (m.p. 141-42°). When the amount of osmic acid is increased in the reaction a keto-acid melting at 88° has been obtained in abundance. This keto-acid has also been prepared by reacting dihydroxyartostanone with hydrogen peroxide in presence of osmic acid. This indicated that the dihydroxy compound is the intermediate product towards the formation of the keto-acid. This may also be noted that though cholestenone can be converted into the monoketo-carboxylic acid of cholestenone by oxidation with potassium permanganate (Windaus *loc. cit.*), artostenone failed to give the monoketo-acid by the same method of procedure. It has been possible, however, to obtain this desired compound through an entirely different intermediary product, the dihydroxyartostanone, by means of hydrogen peroxide in presence of osmic acid. Percentage of nitrogen as estimated from oxime and semicarbazone indicated the presence of one keto group in the keto-acid.

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